

Data Visualization for Oil and Gas Pipeline Anomalies and Repairs using Python BoxIt

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Abstract

In-line inspection (ILI) tools are used to help assess areas of a pipeline that might need remediation. ILI tools are run through the inside of the pipe. As the ILI tool moves down the line, signals travel into the wall and help identify different types of anomalies, such as internal/external corrosion and seam weld defects. The anomalies are sized into “boxes” based on the length and width the ILI tool measures around each location. One of the methods used to estimate corrosion growth between subsequent pig runs, is size and depth comparison of these boxes. BoxIt is a Python web application powered by the interactive visualization capabilities of the Plotly Dash framework. It provides the pipeline industry a visual tool for exploring the relationship between multiple ILI runs to aid in identifying matching anomalies over time. The BoxIt app is available in DNV’s Veracity data-driven and platform-powered path to industry digitalization.

Key Words: Oil, Gas, Pipeline, visualization, in-line inspection

1. Introduction

Risk assessment for oil and gas companies often involves analysis of the structural integrity of transportation pipelines. Because it is cost-prohibited to visually assess the condition of underground pipelines, ILI data play a large role in estimating integrity. Most pipelines are pigged (ILI tool run) every five or seven years, depending on the product, unless there are concerns that would lead to more frequent inspection.

It is difficult for many pipeline operators to be able to “see” the results of a single ILI run other than having an Excel table provide information about the anomalies detected. ILI vendors provide software to aid in the visualization; however, it is specific to the ILI company’s system and takes a trained eye to read the signal data, which often look like heart EKG patterns. Furthermore, these tools do not generally allow viewing of more than a single ILI run even if the same vendor’s tool was used in the ILI runs.

Some larger oil and gas pipeline operators use geographic information systems (GIS) to allow multiple data sets to be overlaid, such as two different ILI runs. In practice, even with large operators, it has proven difficult to get the needed GIS support to easily and quickly show such displays. In addition to ILI data such as length, width, and depth of varying anomaly types, other information may be available that might aid the determination of areas of the pipeline that warrant further study or excavation, which is very costly. Such data includes excavation measurements, repairs, and close interval (above ground) surveys.

At conferences and interactions with clients, it became apparent that an easy-to-use software tool would be welcomed by many users. Such a tool would also have wide

applicability in providing useful insights in the interpretation of large spatial data sets composed of potentially many differing types of data.

Python [1] is a free open-source package used in numerous data sciences projects and handles large data sets. This is an important aspect in being able to incorporate potentially many years of ILI and related data. It was determined that a Python application with Plotly Dash [2] would provide the desired capabilities on an easy-to-use web environment.

BoxIt currently is a visualization only tool that allows multiple ILI runs to be seen simultaneously as well as depicting repairs and other desired pipeline information. The main requirement is that all the data be aligned to the same spatial coordinates.

2. Illustration of Key BoxIt Output

A software tool not described here allows users to input their data into an Excel template that then produces an output file in the format required by BoxIt. Once the BoxIt-ready file is uploaded to BoxIt, the plot of the first pipe segment (“joint”) with data is produced, as shown in Figure 1. Joints of pipeline are different grades of steel in varying diameters and wall thicknesses and are often around 40 feet long. Figure 1 is a portion of a pipeline showing ILI data from both 2012 and 2017. Rectangular boxes are shown for corrosion anomalies for the two years. The 2012 data are colored orange, and the 2017 data are blue. Vertical lines represent girth welds where the ends of two different pipe joints are welded together. Most joints are constructed with longitudinal seam welds that run the length of the joint and could be visualized in BoxIt as a horizontal line if this data is captured in the ILI run.

Figure 1: Sample initial plot produced in BoxIt with some controls seen on the left.

Figure 1 showed a portion of the control panel on the left. The remaining controls are shown in Figure 2 below. The top area of the control panel is where the input file is selected. This can be done either by clicking the dashed box to get a dialog box that allows

navigation to the desired file on the file system, or by dragging a file from a file system window and dropping it on the dashed box. The file is immediately loaded by the app and the file name is displayed below the dashed box. There are five additional categories of controls in the panel: Filter, Joint, Feature, Plot Boundary, & Pipe.

Figure 2: Additional BoxIt control panel options.

The **Filter Controls** (Figure 1) allow the user to limit the data from the current span of pipe that will be plotted. This can be by Feature Type, by ILI Run, or by Depth. The “Feature types” control initially contains all anomaly types as well as repair and replacements (collectively called “features” in the pipeline industry) found on the particular pipeline. Users can decide which features to display on the plot. In this example, there are data from two ILI runs, but users can plot any number of data sets. Not all features are represented by colored rectangles. For instance, sleeves (“SLV” in “Select feature types”) are represented by a gray rectangle that covers a full circumferential section of the pipe, as depicted in Figure 3. In Figure 3 and most of the subsequent plots, the controls the user would see on the left of the screen are not shown.

Figure 3: BoxIt plot including a sleeve completely covering a given circumferential area. The **Joint Controls** (Figure 1) allow the user to navigate to a specific joint by either entering a joint ID or using the arrows to advance or retreat one joint at a time along the length of the pipe. If the “Joints w/Features” checkbox is checked the arrows will skip any

joints that do not have data. Many pipelines have features only on a small subset of joints and thus having this flexibility can reduce the time needed to review a given line.

The **Feature Controls** (Figure 2) allow the user to navigate to a specific feature on the pipe, provided the ILI year and the Feature # are known. The ILI year must be selected from the dropdown menu and then the Feature # can be entered. In the case where there are several features in the same general location, the “Locate Feature” checkbox can be checked. When this is done a pair of vertical and horizontal dashed lines (crosshairs) will be plotted that identify the location of the selected feature, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: A selected feature is located by red, dashed crosshairs.

The **Plot Boundary Controls** (Figure 2) are the final navigation controls, allowing the user to specify a pipe location by odometer. It is these controls that also set the width of the plot (in feet). There are also right and left arrows here, but rather than moving up and down the pipe by joint they move by odometer. The amount that moved is a percentage of the width (specified as a multiple of 5 between 0 and 100).

The **Pipe Controls** (Figure 2) allow the user to rotate the plot circumferentially (in increments of 30 degrees). The “top 2/3 of pipe” checkbox will color the part of the plot that represents the top 2/3 of pipe with a light shade of green as shown in Figures 5 and 6.

Figure 5: Joint 60 has several features at the top of pipe that are split by the default view.

Figure 6: Pipe rotation allows better viewing of anomalies crossing top of the pipe.

Figure 6 depicts the same part of the pipeline in Figure 5 rotated by 60 degrees, providing a clearer view of the joint 60 features. It also shows the top 2/3 of pipe with a green background.

As outlined above, there are several modes to navigate to desired locations along the pipe, such as by joint number, feature #, odometer, or navigation controls. If the user inputs a joint number not in the data set, the text in the “Joint #” box representing the bad joint number will turn red as shown in Figure 7. Similar behavior will occur for an invalid Feature #.

Figure 7: Invalid joint identification by BoxIt in response to user input error.

Another significant form of interaction available to the user is suggested by the instruction that appears above the plot in Figure 1: “Click & drag in top plot to see zoom in 2nd plot.”

The user can highlight any portion of the plot that is of interest by clicking and dragging over an area. A second zoomed plot and associated data table will appear under the top plot. This is especially helpful to take a more in-depth view of a particular part of the pipeline. Doing so helps the visual assessment of features that might align between two or more ILI runs. The data table contains important information of the highlighted features that can be used for integrity assessment. Figure 8 shows a main plot with a selected area. The edges of the selection each have a ‘handle’ that can be clicked and dragged to move that edge to update what is shown in the second plot.

2D Interactive Plot

Figure 8: Main plot showing a selected area to be shown in the zoomed plot.

The resulting zoomed plot that appears under the top one from Figure 8 is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Zoomed plot from selected area of main plot shown in Figure 8.

Below the zoomed plot will appear a table of the selected data. This table can be manipulated in three ways. Individual columns can be hidden, rows can be filtered by typing constraint formulas in the “Filter data...” row of any column, and displayed data can be exported to an Excel file. The table corresponding to Figure 9 is shown below in Figure 10.

ILI Year	Feature #	Joint #	Odometer	Orientation	Surface	Feature Type	Depth %
2012	4	50	90.6	72	E	ML	10
2012	5	50	91	150	E	ML	11
2012	7	50	91.1	120	E	ML	13
2012	8	50	91.4	125	E	ML	15
2012	10	50	91.74	98	E	ML	13
2017	2	50	90.61	65	E	ML	16
2017	3	50	91.05	148	E	ML	18
2017	4	50	91.03	95	E	ML	15
2017	5	50	91.75	90	E	ML	21
2017	6	50	90	148	E	ML	10

Figure 10: Data table from zoomed plot shown in Figure 9.

3. BoxIt Future

BoxIt in its current form has been described in this paper. From this the reader can obtain a reasonable understanding of the capabilities of BoxIt, especially if in-line inspection data for pipelines is not a new topic. DNV is in the process of putting BoxIt into the Veracity open industry digital platform (Veracity, 2024 [3]). The next improvements to the app may include analytics, such as corrosion growth estimation, that is a high demand output.

References

- [1] Van Rossum, G., Drake Jr, F. L. 1995, Python reference manual. Centrum voor Wiskunde en Informatica Amsterdam.
- [2] Plotly Technologies Inc., “Dash”, 2024, <https://dash.plotly.com/>
- [3] Veracity, 2024, <https://www.dnv.com/data-platform/index>
- [4] Harper, William V., Adriana Nenciu, Benjamin Hanna, “Data Visualization for Oil and Gas Pipeline Anomalies and Repairs using R Shiny”, Proceedings of the Joint Statistical Meetings (JSM2019 - Section on Physical and Engineering Sciences), Denver, Colorado: American Statistical Association, pp. 1983-1991.